

Progress Report Space4You

SPOKE 1 – Aerospace and sustainable mobility

DELIVERABLE D3.2.b

NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

PROGRESS REPORT FLAGSHIP

PROJECT [Space4You]

SPOKE 1 - Aerospazio e mobilità sostenibile

DELIVERABLE D3.2.b

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

1. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

1.1 OBJECTIVES

The proposed laboratory, Space4You, shall tackle the challenges stemming out from the great attention devoted by the industry to Space and the consequential opportunities. The initial set-up of the lab addressed several different aspects related to the consolidation of the research work of the different teams and the coordination in a unified framework able to provide solutions for increasing the capabilities and outcomes of small satellites missions.

In particular the work is developed in the areas of:

- Design of space architectures for supporting innovative applications and services
- Development of technologies, materials, equipment, and processes for preparation and sustainable implementation of new applications
- Solutions for increasing autonomy of space habitats

As part of the Research Booster methodology of NODES, Space4You will carry out applied research activities with and for companies, to ensure an effective interaction between leading universities and research centers, scientific and industrial associations, important players from the industry, society, and policy makers. It will nurture ideas, inventions, and innovations generated in universities and transfer them to the industrial and social networks, fostering the relations, synergies, and cross-fertilization between different sectors.

During the reporting period, most tasks have been started within all Research Modules, and initial results of the research activity have been produced, such as papers presented at conferences and journal articles, databases, and preliminary lab models. A first deliverable of the project (D1 – Space4You Lab description) was issued in July 2023. The details of the activities and of the achievements are given in Section 1.2 and in the annexes.

1.2 WORK CARRIED OUT PER RM IN THE REPORTING PERIOD

1.2.1 Research Module 0

Research Module n.0	Start month: M1				End month: M36			
Title: SETUP AND IMPLEMENTATION OF SPACE4YOU LAB								
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y - Partially								
RM Leader	PoliTO							
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo	Links	PoliBa				
Type of action:	Industrial Research							
Effort in person/months:	9.39	2.28	0.62	2.40				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):								
<p>Activities to coordinate the research teams and to set up the distributed laboratory.</p> <p>Applied research activities that are functional to a better understanding of the dynamics of technology transfer and new business creation in the new space industry.</p>								
<u>Task 0.1 Lab setup and management</u>								
PoliTO/ DET and DIMEAS								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation and issue of deliverable D1, and working on D4 • Preparation of periodic progress reports (M6 and M12) • Preparation of the dissemination material presented to the companies during the dissemination events, maintenance of a collaborative tool for documents management and meeting organization through a dedicated Microsoft Teams group involving all the participants in the project • Organization of periodic internal meetings • Cooperation with other Spokes of NODES for the coordination of the professional education activities • Dissemination and engagement activities towards the aerospace companies of the NODES ecosystem 								
All partners/Research teams								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation to internal meetings to present and coordinate the different research activities. • Contribution to Deliverable D1 and D4 • Establishment of procurement procedures for the improvement of new instrumentation for the research labs 								

Task 0.2 Ecosystem development

PolìTO/DIGEP: The research activities for this task focuses on understanding the key factors influencing the process of creating and growing new businesses in the aerospace sector. These factors involve both new business opportunities generated by technological changes and the dynamics of localized interaction among various actors in the innovation ecosystem.

In particular, during the reporting period the research activities have focussed on the analysis of the determinants of business success of European startups operating in the aerospace domain. To achieve these objectives, two databases, "SpaceStartups" and "SpaceInvestors," were completed, while a third database "PatentSpace", related to patent applications in space technologies, is currently under development. The "SpaceStartups" is a new database containing information on 339 EU-based startups that were founded in the past 10 years and are operating within the space sector. In the "SpaceInvestors" database we have compiled data on VC and corporate investors in Europe who have made equity investments in aerospace startups. In the "PatentSpace" database we are in the final stages of collecting patent data related to the space sector. The data has been sourced through the Clarivate database.

Such data have been used for the development of 3 papers, outlined below.

The first paper empirically addresses the role of founders' characteristics on the firm's performance for deep-tech startups operating in the New Space domain. Specifically, the aim is to understand the extent to which the set of prior competencies and knowledge backgrounds can influence the fundraising success of startups. The study is based on a sample of 390 startups founded in Europe since 2013 that have been classified according to the typology of business and the features of the founding team.

The second paper address a specific technology, artificial intelligence, that has a great application potential in the solution for the new space economy startups. In particular, adopting an innovation ecosystem approach, the paper addresses the correlation between university activity in AI and the nature of the innovations carried out by co-localised startups.

The third paper provides an in-depth review of extant studies in the economics of innovation and management literature on the aerospace industry, with a focus on a key innovation driver for the industry, namely sustainability of space activities. The analysis revealed that in general, there is a slight prevalence of articles that primarily focused on space as the main locus of research rather than Earth.

PoliBA/DMMM: The activity focused on reviewing the state of the art regarding the topic of business model applied to the space domain. In particular, the research team conducted a literature review on business model and business model innovation with a focus on the papers using the space domain as research setting. The review was performed by searching specific keywords (such as, “business model” – “business model innovation” – “space”) on online databases of scientific papers. The research team defined a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria which were applied to the collected papers in order to come up with a set of documents useful to reach the goal of the analysis (i.e., coping the state of the art about business model and business model innovation in the space domain). The resulting list of papers was critically analyzed in order to define the boundary of knowledge in the emerging topic of how existing and new companies are structuring their business models to enter and/or to be competitive in the new space economy. The obtained results will be used as a knowledge base to perform the activities which will be carried on in the following steps of the project.

Task 0.3 Assessment and sustainability

PoliTO/DIGEP: This task is meant to support the evaluation the project's results and put them into a broader perspective of future exploitation, while also planning future activities according to the availability of the laboratory and its possible growth.

During the reporting period, the objectives were pursued by collecting data and conducting an updated literature review to highlight key innovation trends in the industry.

Output and results

Datasets creation:

1. "SpaceStartups": This is a new database containing information on 339 EU-based startups that were founded in the past 10 years and are operating within the space sector. We collected this data from the Dealroom database.
2. "SpaceInvestors": We have compiled data on VC and corporate investors in Europe who have made equity investments in aerospace startups. Most of our information comes from Dealroom as a data source.
3. "PatentSpace": The completed database is expected to contain approximately 25,000 patents filed with the European Patent Office over the last 10 years.

Journal Publications:

1. “When computer science is not enough: universities knowledge specializations behind artificial intelligence startups in Italy” (details in dedicated section)

Presentations in Scientific Conferences

- R&D Management Conference 2023, “Responsible and Responsive Innovation for a Better Future”, Seville 19-21 June 2023.
- NanoInnovation International Conference, Rome, 20th September 2023

- XXXIV Annual Scientific Meeting - RSA AiIG 2023, "Humanizing technologies for a better society. Purpose-driven innovation to empower people", Lecco, October 12-13, 2023.
- RENT XXXVII "TAMING UNCERTAINTY", Gdansk, Poland, 15-17 November 2023

Deviations (if applicable):

The deliverable D4 (Web-site and knowledge portal) has been delayed due to issues in the configuration of a proper infrastructure to host the portal. Notwithstanding the technical problem related to the implementation and deployment of the portal, the content of the web pages is under preparation.

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

- Finalisation of D4
- Completion of the database PatentSpace on patent applications at European level.
- Development of an econometric paper that through the exploitation of the PatentSpace database analyzes the extent of technology transfer from space to terrestrial activities and vice-versa. The analyses will be based on the tracking of patent citations patterns as a proxy of underlying knowledge flows.
- Presentation of Space4You to the Stakeholder Committee

1.2.2 Research Module 1

Research Module n.1	Start month: M4				End month: M36			
Title: DESIGN								
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y - partially								
RM Leader	PoliTO							
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo	Links	PoliBA				
Type of action:	Industrial Research							
Effort in person/months:	2.28	2.08	1.33	2.40				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):								
Research studies to support the DESIGN phase of space systems and missions.								
<u>Task 1.1 Concurrent & virtual design</u>								
<p>PoliTO/DIMEAS: The requirements for the improvement of the existing Concurrent Engineering System (CES) have been consolidated. Main drivers will be: 1) reusability of the facility across multiple projects, 2) traceability of requirements, 3) applicability of the facility across project phases (ideally up to phase B / PDR), and 4) usability of the facility by multiple users / operators in a distributed environment. Main software tools have been identified for supporting the implementation. A shortlist of possible use cases has been developed including a CubeSat mission for EO, a Cubesat mission for in orbit servicing, and a CubeSat mission for science at the Moon. A database of CubeSat technologies (CUTE-DB) has been created (draft version), and it will be completed by the end of the project in its final version. The database will be integrated in the CES in the next period, and continuously maintained throughout the activity.</p>								
<u>Task 1.2 Simulation models</u>								
<p>PoliTO/DISMA: In the reporting period the work on the development of numerical schemes for coupled 3D-2D PDE problems on complex geometries was continued, with the final goal of a simulation tool code capable of handling arbitrarily complex configurations.</p> <p>Methods based on polygonal/polyhedral meshes are another promising strategy for domain decomposition strategies. In particular, a quite recent method, called the Virtual Element Method (VEM), appears particularly appealing, since sharing the same setting of the well established FEM. A redefinition of the basis function for the VEM has been investigated and proposed to improve the robustness of the method in presence of distorted and highly elongated elements. This is of particular importance for the simulation of realistic configurations, with intersecting interfaces. This research led to a publication on the Journal Mathematics in Engineering.</p>								

Polito/DIMEAS: At system level some specific simulation modelling techniques for thermal systems have been developed. In particular, commercial tools for thermal analysis have been adapted to consider the effects of the lunar soil thermal radiation on the futuristic infrastructures on the Moon surface (power generation systems, habitats, rovers and mechatronics, etc..) inspired to the NASA ARTEMIS scenario. Referring to some applications (thermal radiators of power generation systems, windows for pressurized modules, and on-board components for exploration rovers) special engineering thermal models have been developed with the definition of useful temperature measurement points to implement suitable thermal control laws and to detect thermal functions degradation. Moreover, different models of the thermal system have been developed and integrated using both a lumped parameter formulation and a finite element description, in a multi-fidelity approach.

LINKS/CPE: In literature, several approaches to perform the analysis of high-resolution images from a satellite constellation can be found, with a particular focus on the creation of a 3D model that can be used as a basis for a twin digital model. With standard approaches, the computational time becomes too high when dealing with very high precision images covering large areas, therefore a HPC approach is required. Among the possibilities, we tested a solution provided by nFrames called SURE. The solution is being tested on images representing Parco Dora in Torino, with the construction of the 3D model of the park. The same approach can be used to implement the 3D model of the entire city of Torino. Moreover, this 3D model is a perfect starting point to realize a real digital twin that can be used to simulate different application scenarios.

UNITO/Math: On the computational approach to symmetric solutions for the N-body problem, the following has been carried out. The steps of the procedure to follow have been established in agreement with machine learning experts, numerical analysts, and theoretical colleagues. Progress has been made in implementing a large database for periodic trajectories. Routines for numerical computations in Python language of stability indicators have been developed to facilitate the clustering of the orbits in the database, based on their stability complexity. These are essential for implementing the next machine learning procedure. Up to this point, a portion of the project code has been produced and uploaded to the following repository: <https://github.com/LimenResearch/norbit>.

Poliba/DMMM: The preliminary research activity of the project concerned the literature review of hypersonic re-entry for Earth and Mars atmospheres. Chemical kinetics models available in the literature have been analyzed to identify the most suitable one for the project's purposes. Such models mainly follow a macroscopic approach, known as multitemperature approach as it is very easy to implement and cheap with respect to more sophisticated State-to-State models. The

problem of thermochemical non-equilibrium is linked to the different energy modes involved during the hypersonic flight, namely translational, rotational, vibrational, and electronic modes. Moreover, chemical dissociation and ionization make the problem even more complicated. The knowledge of pros and cons of the models available in the literature is essential in the view of the development of a computational tool able to perform high fidelity simulations of hypersonic flows. Not least, many fluid dynamics problems involve bluff body flows, which are known to be turbulent in the wake region (downstream of the body). Finally, dealing with complex gas mixtures, an accurate transport model must be devised to evaluate diffusion coefficients (viscosity, conductivity, diffusivity). Chapman-Enskog expansion represents a very accurate tool for such a goal, even if the calculation is quite demanding. Hence, as a first attempt, classical mixing rules are a valid alternative.

Activities are ongoing to find an efficient way to couple thermochemical and turbulence models and implement them in a 3D fluid dynamic solver. Such a tool is expected to run on both CPUs and GPUs so that the computational time required by the numerical simulations is drastically reduced.

Task 1.3 ICT technologies

Polito/DET: A packet-based level simulator for satellite networks is considered for the initial assessment of scalability. The main modeling assumptions to include in the simulator are investigated, in order to include a communication model and a mobility model with the best compromise between performance accuracy and simulator scalability.

LINKS/CPE: During the reporting period, the configuration of the server rack has been completed. Based on an Open Stack architecture, a group of servers equipped with both high-performance CPUs and GPUs has been configured as an HPC node that can be used as an asset for the distributed laboratory. The server architecture will provide the necessary hardware resources to run simulations and/or to develop digital twin models, based, for example, on very high-resolution digital images. The server configuration has been tested in order to achieve the best performance according to image data processing as a first example of service that can be provided with such an architecture. However, hardware resources can be specifically configured to address the challenges of other simulation scenarios, becoming a useful tool to support local SMEs and industries in their business activities.

Task 1.4 Generic technologies

Polito/DIMEAS: The requirements for novel visual navigation algorithms for proximity operations of small distributed systems in safety-critical context have been consolidated for a specific

mission. The selected use case refers to a nanosatellite performing rendezvous and docking mission with a larger mothercraft in Low Earth Orbit.

Polito/DIMEAS: Leveraging on the background experience of the Photonext interdepartmental center the optic measurement of the temperature of space subsystems has been thorough, in particular, the FBG sensing technology. Some FBG sensors packaging techniques have been specifically designed for the temperature measurement of radiators, windows and tanks of lunar infrastructures and power generation systems.

Some proposed sensors packaging solution for the thermal monitoring by FBG of transparent windows of spacecraft have been proposed. A preliminary thermal testing of specimens into a thermal chamber has been conducted to allow the model validation and to test the suitability of the proposed packaging techniques. A possible communication network for the distribution of the sensors information has been conceived to allow thermal management and control activities. In particular, the share of the information via a WiFi network with augmented reality tools has been conceived to support the astronauts in decision making.

Polito/DISEG: Based on the experience of the Materials and Fracture Mechanics Lab and the ArtStE - Artificial Intelligence in Structural Engineering lab at DISEG Department, the validity of augmented reality media for the realization of three-dimensional mockups of space habitat shapes was evaluated. In particular, a 3D holographic visualization solution was developed, realized by means of a high-speed, high-frequency rotating holographic projector. At the same time, DIC cameras were used to characterize three-point bending tests for simulants materials and specimens. The strain field results are statically correlated with traditional output data obtained during the three-PBT tests. An infrared (IR) camera integrated with the DIC cameras will be evaluated, which enables accurate acquisition and analysis of temperature data along with full-field strain and deformation data. The system works by first calibrating the intrinsic optical parameters of the IR camera and then calibrating the position of the IR camera relative to the DIC system. This triangulation allows the VIC-3D to position the thermal and strain data, as well as the 3D surface data, in a common coordinate system.

UniTO/Chemistry: During the reporting period, preliminary investigations about advanced materials for the development of innovative solar cells have been started. Some light-absorbing dyes for dye-sensitized solar cells, based on organic polymethines, have been designed and are currently in development. The study of different formulations for liquid and quasi-solid electrolytes based on water and organic gelators is ongoing.

PoliBA/DMMM: In the reporting period, Poliba has started the research activities related to the development of innovative technologies aimed at increasing the autonomy of rovers for planetary exploration. A comprehensive analysis of the state-of-the-art in the locomotion architectures currently adopted for planetary rovers has been developed, highlighting advantages and disadvantages. The main solutions proposed in the Literature for terrain estimation have been also reviewed. This review will serve as a starting point towards the development of new technologies to improve rover autonomy from both hardware and software perspectives.

Output and results:

PoliTO/DIMEAS: draft version of the CubeSat technology database (CUTE-DB)

PoliTO/DISMA: development of numerical schemes for coupled 3D-2D PDE problems on complex geometries

PoliTO/DIMEAS: Validation of the thermal models by testing in thermal chamber using a novel measurement technique via FBG optical sensors, suitable to implement an effective thermal monitoring and control in space. Packaging techniques of FBG sensors for thermal measurement in space.

LINKS/CPE: 3D models for digital twin creation

UniTO/Math: Software for numerical computations in Python language of stability indicators to facilitate the clustering of the orbits

LINKS/CPE: Servers, based on an Open Stack architecture, equipped with both high-performance CPUs and GPUs has been configured as an HPC node that can be used as an asset for the distributed laboratory.

PoliTO/DISEG: 3D holographic visualization solution was developed for mockups of space habitats

Conference publications:

- Alessandro Aimasso, Giacomo Gallone, Matteo D.L. Dalla Vedova and Paolo Maggiore, "Experimental analysis of Fiber Bragg Grating sensors thermal calibration under different loading conditions", 10th MetroAerospace 2023, IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for AeroSpace, Milano, 19-21 June 2023.
- Antonio Costantino Marceddu, Alessandro Aimasso, Antonio Scaldasferri, Paolo Maggiore, Bartolomeo Montrucchio, Matteo D. L. Dalla Vedova; "Creation of a Support Software for the Development of a System for Sending and Visualizing FBG Sensor Data for Aerospace Application"; 10th MetroAerospace 2023, IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for AeroSpace, Milano, 19-21 June 2023.

Deviations (if applicable):

No Deviations from initial planning

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

PolITO/DIMEAS: Development of the calculation modules to be integrated into the Concurrent Engineering System (CES). Selection of one reference use case to be used for the validation of the improved CES. Population of the CubeSat Technology Database (CUTE-DB).

PolITO/DIMEAS: Development of the first version of the navigation algorithm(s)

1.2.2 Research Module 2

Research Module n.2	Start month: M4				End month: M36			
Title: DEVELOPMENT								
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y/N								
RM Leader	PoliTO							
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo	Links	PoliBa				
Type of action:	Industrial Research							
Effort in person/months:	22.63	0.4	0.0	2.40				

Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):

Research studies to support the DEVELOPMENT phase of space systems and missions.

Task 2.1 Manufacturing processes

PoliTO/DIMEAS: DIMEAS unit reviewed the existing competences and facilities of the distributed lab and defined the activities concerning the surface plasma treatment of composite materials, in particular carbon or glass fibre fabrics for composites with 30% biocontent epoxy matrix.

Preliminary tests on carbon fibre fabric (treated and untreated) and standard specimens were carried out to preliminary assess the effect of the plasma treatment of fabrics on the mechanical properties of the composite materials. Micro Raman and Fourier Transform Infrared – Attenuated Total Reflectance (FTIR-ATR) spectroscopy showed that the functional groups and active sites grafted onto the surface after plasma treatment, and mechanical tests of resistance to delamination to quantify the improvement in terms of fibre-matrix adhesion. An increase in the fracture toughness of 4% and 3.3% in mode I and II were obtained respectively, as well as 16.1% and 14.3% increase in maximum load at first crack propagation. Thus, an optimisation of the parameters related to the plasma treatment should be developed to maximise the mechanical properties.

A methodology for optimising the parameters (distance plasma jet – component, gas flow rate, exposure time, ionization power) adopted during the plasma treatment of fibre fabrics has been developed. This optimisation procedure involves the Design of Experiment (DoE) that uses the generation of a grid of parameters to which physical values, obtained by spectroscopic and mechanical characterization, are associated. The research of an optimal point is carried out by studying the polynomial function related to the physical and mechanical characterization, and the consequent Response Surface Methodology (RSM) application.

PoliTO/DISAT (LINCE): Within the reference period, LINCE team addressed its efforts on two different fronts, one aimed at defining the state of the art of ceramic vat-photopolymerization technologies for space and aerospace applications and the other dedicated to preliminary

experiments aimed at identifying suitable printing parameters set for the future development of functional ceramic systems by Digital Light Processing (DLP).

Literature search outlined the role of ceramics and ceramic composites in relevant advanced technological fields of our time. This led to the publication of one review paper in *Frontiers in Materials*, providing a transversal analysis of the state-of-the-art of the applications of vat-photopolymerization technologies, namely, stereolithography (SL) and DLP in several industrial/research fields, including space/aerospace and energy/environment, providing readers a transfer of knowledge and “lessons learned” from one field to the other.

Based on this, LINCE targeted the experimental work on the production of alternative functional ceramic systems for the selective capture of CO₂ produced by human crew during space missions and the implementation of smart regeneration strategies post-capture.

First, ceramic substrates based on zirconia, alumina and mullite were produced by DLP. Ceramic particles were suspended within photocurable liquid monomers and used as solid loading for obtaining photocurable ceramic resins. In this preliminary phase, optimal slurry composition and printing parameter set for producing complex porous structure with refined microstructure were defined. The effect of ball milling process, performed to obtain a finely-dispersed powder with controlled submicrometric particle size distribution, was deeply investigated to define its role in affecting powder surface properties, slurries rheology, curing depth and, consequently, green/fired properties. Effective strategies based on the implementation of specific heat treatments upstream of the printing have been designed to manage delamination issues encountered as a result of ball milling process.

Part of these preliminary results was presented at the XVIII Conference & Exhibition of the European Ceramic Society, Lyon, 2-6 July 2023 (France).

PoliTO/DISAT (Glance): During this reporting period, Glance Group (DISAT) conducted a comprehensive assessment of the distributed lab's current capabilities and resources. Subsequently, Glance outlined specific initiatives focused on the study of surface plasma treatment of ceramic based materials as well as on C reinforced polymeric composite materials, in collaboration with DIMEAS department.

The activity aims at exploring plasma-based solutions for improving the joint strength of joined components by inducing a new surface texture able to promote interlocking; moreover, it pays special attention to identifying treatments that can be implemented at an industrial scale.

In particular, silicon carbide (SiC) was investigated. It is attracting a great deal of interest in advanced technological applications as aerospace, because of its outstanding thermomechanical properties and lightweight. Nevertheless, the application of SiC-based materials depends on the ability to join them, in many cases, because manufacturing these materials as large components, with complicated shapes, is extremely difficult and expensive. A critical issue for the broader use

of SiC is thus the development of joining methods to assemble large components in complex structures.

To manufacture a reliable product, promoting optimal adhesion between the parts to be joined and the joining material is critical. This can be promoted by a preliminary preparation of the surface and in particular by modifying the surface texture and chemistry. We investigated the effectiveness of plasma-based solutions as techniques to improve SiC joints strength. The effectiveness of the plasma treatment to strengthen the joining can be attributed to the formation of this thin silica film, which creates a mechanical anchoring system when penetrated by the adhesive. In the reported activity, zeta potential measurements, in combination with microscopical analysis, were applied to characterize SiC surfaces and adhesive to understand more in-depth the eventual chemical interaction between the surface and the adhesive, proposing for the first time, to the best of our knowledge, this technique for characterizing surfaces and adhesives before joining.

Polito/DISEG: Team's contribution referred to the definition of the best instrumentation suitable for 3D realization of optimized structures models using 3D printing and additive manufacturing procedures based on simulant materials. First, suitable compounds were defined for the realization of specimens suitable for experimentation. Many of these simulants were considered on specific planetary areas, trying to increase the degree of verisimilitude in terms of material properties. The research group is working on the design of a dome structure made by a form-finding method for the realization of the extraterrestrial habitat. This structure is designed by evaluating an optimized dome shape based on the multi-body rope approach (MRA). The MRA method consists of a system of masses interconnected through rope elements. The choice of the material proposed for the dome follows the requirements of the in-situ resource utilization (ISRU) approach. The idea is to prepare a concrete-like material using local materials for both aggregates and binder, and a proposal is made for Mars exploration. The aggregate can be made from the local regolith, whose composition can be roughly simulated by a basaltic sand, choosing the correct granulometry observed by the exploration missions. Regarding the binder two possibilities are considered: a CaSO₄-based binder, that could exploit the gypsum dunes observed in the north of the planet; a binder based on iron-sulfate, that is widely spread on the surface of Mars, and that was never reported before as a possible material for Mars ISRU. At the moment, considering a final material configuration also constituted by the inclusion of natural fibers in the mix, compressive and flexural strength tests will be carried out to evaluate the response of the compounds under operating conditions of the dome compatible with the service life of the structure in the extra-terrestrial habitat. The use of natural fibers is also explored in order to explore the possibility of making self-assembling and self-supporting smart structures for emergency scenarios.

Task 2.2 smart AIV/T

PolìTO/DIMEAS: A Model & Simulation Based tool (a hybrid SIL-HIL simulator) has been chosen as main tool for implementing the verification and validation process of space technologies. A simulator is already available within the research group at DIMEAS and has proved to be effective for GNC systems development. Requirements for the updated simulator have been defined to enable the verification of visual navigation algorithms.

The electronics is the most important source of defects during AIV/T activities, with specific reference to soldering process. The definition of strategies for supporting the verification and testing of small space systems has been defined, with specific reference to the electronic boards, and SMD soldering process, as well as the thermal testing effectiveness. The objective is to reduce the duration and the cost of the verification/testing campaign, while increasing the effectiveness of the verification/testing activities, with the final goal of increasing mission success. In particular, a space grade representative geometry of an electronic board, and a specific soldering process, have been selected to implement a set of experiments, with statistical significance, and to study how the number and amplitude of thermal cycles can enucleate the possible defects into soldering joints. The design of experiments of the tests has been defined. Therefore, a test campaign has been planned and it will start using a thermal chamber, available at DIMEAS laboratories, to define the best defects screening technique.

Task 2.3 ICT Technologies

PolìTO/DAUIN: Research activities in ICT technologies were dedicated to investigating the fault tolerance of deep Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and specifically the effect of several design choices including the choice of architecture, the training protocol, and the quantization. Despite their distributed and parallel nature, CNNs are not intrinsically tolerant to radiation-induced transient faults. In the absence of fault mitigation techniques, their accuracy was shown to drop dramatically even at low fault rates. Replication and redundancy, either at the hardware or software level, are effective but expensive solutions. However, recent works have shown that changes in the CNN architectures and/or training procedure may achieve a better trade-off between accuracy and fault tolerance. In particular, several techniques have been proposed to improve CNN's resilience to faults by constraining the activation range of intermediate layers. Understandably, the current literature has so far focused on simple benchmarks, such as CIFAR-10 or CIFAR-100, relatively shallow CNNs, and standard training procedures. In the first year, we performed a comprehensive experimental investigation of the fault tolerance of CNNs under more realistic experimental conditions. Transient faults (in the form of bit flips) were simulated at the software level after optimizing the injection technique by considering the statistical distribution of the errors. Experiments were conducted on several publicly available datasets, from

the well-known ImageNet classification task to several EO benchmarks. Design choices that were experimentally investigated included the architecture (ResNet-50, VGG13, DenseNet161, InceptionV3), choice of pre-training (standard supervised setting vs. pretraining via self-supervised learning – SSL), choice of activation clipping function (Relu6 vs. ClipAct), quantization (32 bit vs. 8 bit). Experimental results have gained novel insights on the trade-off between accuracy and fault tolerance. For instance, SSL pre-training combined with activation clipping increases fault tolerance compared to standard supervised learning, while at the same time better preserving accuracy. On the other hand, quantization drastically increases fault tolerance, but reduces baseline accuracy, especially when applied after SSL pretraining. The results have been submitted for publication at DATE (Design, Automation and Test in Europe Conference) 2024, and are currently being extended for submission to a journal.

PoliTO/DET: During this first year of the project the development of a physical layer signal simulator started. These software elements are being integrated in the software-defined radio reconfigurable test-bench for testing communication architectures tailored to small satellites, intended for employment both within Earth's orbits and as integral communication nodes in space missions, including, but not limited to, those bound for the Moon village. Signals used for ranging channels are included as well, in order to support the testing of positioning and navigation techniques. The software modules are designed with a flexible approach and currently encompass the generation of signals aligned to the CCSDS recommendations, but also more modern proposals from the scientific literature. As for the navigation part, a revision of the already available Software-defined implementation of GNSS receivers was undertaken in order to simplify interfaces among the different stages, and prepare for seamless integration in the test-bench.

PoliTO/DET: A simulator for a network of cooperative mobile nodes has been developed, which can be considered as fundamental step to develop a simulator for a generic satellite network. The simulator is event-driven and it models the communications between mobile nodes according to a generic channel model. Data transmission is modelled at packet level and no MAC layer is implemented to maximize scalability. Multihop communication is supported. Environmental effects are modelled (e.g., modifying the trajectory of the mobile nodes, or affecting the autonomy of the nodes). Due the high complexity of the mobility of satellite constellations, as initial step the simulator has been aimed at simulating a swarm of cooperative UAVs, with all the modelling assumptions tailored to address satellite networks in the future releases of the software A GUI is also provided to depict the current state of all the mobile nodes.

PoliBA/DEI: Within the scope of Activity 4 of PoliBA in this project, focused on "Space radiation simulation and analysis of photonic devices and systems for space applications", the identification

of key photonic integrated components for use in future satellite missions is currently ongoing. This involves a rigorous analysis of the resistance to electromagnetic radiation of the semiconductor materials commonly employed in the Space domain. The primary goal is to assess the state of the art of these technologies, identify radiation-related challenges they may face, and determine ways to enhance their resilience. The information collected in this phase will be crucial for the selection of subsequent case studies, allowing us to focus our attention on components that offer the highest reliability in the space environment.

Task 2.4 Generic technologies

PoliTO/DIMEAS: Applying the outcomes and the models developed in the previous tasks a technology demonstrator of a space graded multipurpose measurement chain using FBG optical sensors has been implemented: in particular, a test set for the temperature measurement inside Multi Layer Insulator (MLI) and over the surface of transparent glass (simulating a window) has been preliminary arranged in PoliTO DIMEAS laboratories. The study has pointed out a possible sensor packaging technique both for MLI and transparent glass temperature measurements. A test campaign has been planned.

UniTO/DipFisica: The procurement of instrumentation for the enhancement of the X-ray Calibration Facility (XCF), hosted in the Physics Department of UniTO and being part of the distributed Space4You lab, has continued in the second half-year with the acquisition of an Iron-55 source, expected to be delivered in the next months. This will be used for the energy calibration of the detectors, being it capable of illuminating the whole detector, for mapping and monitoring the detectors responses, and in particular the quantum efficiency and the energy resolution. The radiation source currently used in XCF is a multi-anode X-ray tube, that ensures the production of two identical beam lines at different energies: one is unpolarized, the other one passes through a polarizing crystal, becoming polarized. In the last months we have completed a fine tuning of the set-up and we are now implementing the stability test of the radiation source. We are using a SDD and a CMOS camera as monitors of the two beams. We have just started the characterization study of a Gas Pixel Detector, that is similar to those currently flying on the Imaging X-ray Polarimetry Explorer (IXPE). As soon as the Iron-55 source is available, we will complete the energy calibration of the detector and the gain uniformity test of pixels.

PoliBA/DEI: In the context of Activity 5, focused on "Study and design of innovative reconfigurable satellite structures, based on intelligent materials and electronic/photonic sensors and actuators", the primary satellite functionalities that can benefit from "smart system" technology are currently examined. This includes systems for monitoring the integrity of satellite panels following impacts with debris in orbit.

Output and results:

Research results:

- **PoliTO/DIMEAS:** Assessment of the experimental plane (DoE) related to plasma surface treatment, chemical-physical preliminary tests (spectroscopic) and mechanical tests between treated and untreated components.
- **POLITO/DISEG:** design of a dome structure made by a form-finding method for the realization of the extraterrestrial habitat.
- **POLITO/DIMEAS:** definition of effective strategies for supporting the verification and testing of small space systems
- **PoliTO/DET:** simulator for a network of cooperative mobile nodes

Journal publications

- **PoliTO/DISAT (LINCE):** 1 review paper published in Frontiers in Materials (October 9th 2023)

Presentations at Conferences:

- **PoliTO/DISAT (LINCE):** 1 oral contribution to the XVIII Conference & Exhibition of the European Ceramic Society, 2-6 July 2023
- **UniTO/DipFisica:**
 - 1 poster at "IFAE 2023 conference" (Catania, 12-14 April 2023)
 - 1 presentation at "Open Day – Infrastrutture di ricerca UniTO per la sostenibilità, la tecnologia e il benessere" (Torino, 12 Luglio 2023),
 - 1 presentation at "VII National Seminar on Innovative detectors" (Torino, 9-13 October 2023)

Submitted publications:

- PoliTo/DISAT (Glance group) 1 paper ("TEM and Zeta potential titration as suitable techniques for investigating the joining of modified ceramic surfaces.") under Review on Ceramics International (Q1)
- PoliTO/DAUIN: 1 conference submission DATE (Design, Automation and Test in Europe Conference) 2024

Deviations (if applicable):

NONE

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

Polito/DISAT (LINCE): LINCE team will develop a smart system for Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS), through the shaping of ceramic substrates by additive manufacturing (AM) and their subsequent functionalization for CO₂ with Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs), i.e. crystalline materials with ultrahigh porosity and internal surface areas, promising for as storage media for different types of gases. The effect of surface modification treatments on MOFs growth onto the ceramic substrate will be investigated. For the realization of this project, LINCE team has partnered with the Gance Team (DISAT), which will be in charge of surface modification treatments of the ceramic substrate using Corona plasma treatment.

At the same time, the group is consolidating new scientific collaborations supporting the design and advanced characterization of the porous ceramic substrates through Computational Fluid Dynamic analysis for the identification of optimized 3D porous designs, avoiding time-consuming trial and errors approaches, micro-CT and permeability/adsorption testing for evaluating the gas capture efficacy.

Polito/DISAT (Gance group): In the next months, the following activities will be carried out

- Further characterization of surface modified SiC -based materials
- Comparison of morphologies and mechanical strength in SiC based joints with and without surface modification
- characterisation of surface modified samples (CFRP) developed in collaboration with DIMEAS department
- definition of a methodology for the plasma surface modification of ceramic substrates to promote MOFs growth, in collaboration with Lince group (DISAT).

Polito/DIMEAS: Review of design / update of existing models for GNC miniaturised systems. Definition of new simulation models needed for the improvement of the simulator's capabilities.

Polito/DIMEAS: implementation and verification of the DoE; comparison of the spectroscopic surface characterization methodologies already implemented with similar and different types thanks to the collaboration with the DISAT department.

Polito/DAUIN: We will continue to investigate the fault-tolerance of different CNNs in order to extend the current submission to a journal. A more realistic fault model will be developed considering the properties of the underlying hardware platform, and the analysis will be further expanded towards other types of deep neural networks, beyond CNNs.

Polito/DET: finalisation of the signal simulator including both the physical layer and the networking layer

1.2.2 Research Module 3

Research Module n.3	Start month: M4				End month: M36			
Title: OPERATIONS								
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y/N								
RM Leader	PoliTO							
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo	Links	PoliBa				
Type of action:	Industrial Research							
Effort in person/months:	1.33	0.0	0.0	0.0				
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):								
Research studies to support the OPERATIONS phase of space systems and missions.								
<u>Task 3.1 Autonomous operation</u>								
Activities for this task are scheduled to start on the second year of the project.								
<u>Task 3.2 Ground infrastructure</u>								
PoliTO/DIMEAS: The operations management system (or Mission Control Centre – MCC) of the CubeSat Control Centre – C3 has been finalised and tested on a real application, that is the Spei Satelles mission. The system has been used to prepare commands and to process housekeeping and mission data. The C3 MCC at PoliTO is composed of core software managing the interaction with the operators, the generation of the command to be sent to the radio interfaces, and the storage and analysis of the raw data. If the received packets are not corrupted, they are decoded, and the values are displayed in real-time on a dedicated window. On the other hand, if the packets are not decodable, they are automatically saved in various formats, allowing post-processing and decoding. Other functions of the MCC software are the coordination of tracking tasks and the management of the radiofrequency front-end. The radiofrequency part of C3 has also been tested in the lab, while the Ground to Space (G2S) and Space to Ground (S2G) radiofrequency chains are still under development.								
<u>Task 3.3 Data management</u>								
PoliTO/DISMA: In some applications there is a large quantity of data that are however not homogeneous, and thus require a de-featuring operation before the dat, e.g. in machine learning. Such de-featuring process however usually is performed empirically. A mathematical and statistical analysis on such process seems still not available. Moreover, in some cases, the presence of different features in data can be beneficial, especially for classification problems. An analysis on this subject is being performed, aiming at the definition of an optimum, if this exists, similar								

investigation can be performed to provide a mathematical background for data augmentation processes.

PoliTO/DAUIN: Data management innovation is nowadays driven by the application of AI/ML/DL solutions for several applications that require, fast and reliable analysis of large amount of data, statistical characterization, and automated decision support. In this context, it is envisioned that data processing will be performed both on board and/or on ground. Activities on this task focused primarily on the robustness of on-board processing, in connection with activities on Task 2.3. Specifically, experiments were conducted to investigate the effectiveness of self-supervised pretraining (SSL) and quantization on accuracy and robustness of convolutional neural networks for EO tasks. However, we discovered that while both SSL and quantization increase tolerance to transient faults, the combination of the two techniques results negatively affect accuracy. Investigations on techniques that combine SSL and quantization-aware training for optimal and robust performance in EO classification tasks.

Output and results:

Research results

- **PoliTO/DIMEAS:** C3 MCC delivered and tested in operative conditions. More than 7000 packets handled from June to August 2023.

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations from the initial planning

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

PoliTO/DIMEAS: to start the integration of the C3 UHF antenna and RF equipment.

1.2.2 Research Module 4

Research Module n.4	Start month: M4				End month: M36			
Title: EXPLOITATION								
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y/N								
RM Leader	PoliTO							
Partners involved	PoliTo	UniTo	Links	PoliBa				
Type of action:	Industrial Research							
Effort in person/months:	6.86	0.4	0.4	0.0				

Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):

Research studies to support the EXPLOITATION phase of space systems and missions.

Task 4.1. Modern satellite communication services

PoliTO/DET: Different approaches are considered to evaluate the performance in terms of delays and throughput for a network of cooperative satellites. (i) Formal methods based on time-space graphs, designed specifically for Delay Tolerant Networks (DTN). The models are tailored to periodic mobility, motivated by the periodicity of satellite orbits. (ii) Specific libraries, tailored for satellite networks, developed for generic network simulators (e.g., OMNet++). In this case, scalability issues arise due to the low level implementation of the network protocols. Thus, the approach shows some limitation for large satellite constellation scenarios. (iii) Ad-hoc simulators can be developed for the considered network scenarios to achieve the desired compromise between complexity and model accuracy. An initial version based on event-driven approach has been developed, tailored for a simplified scenario, and an initial scalability assessment has been performed, showing the limited scalability of the approach, suggesting that a combination of formal methods and event-driven simulation must be evaluated in the next year of the project.

Task 4.2 Earth Observation

PoliTO/DIMEAS: Spatial interpolation techniques for the mapping of offshore parameters have been developed and tested using simulated datasets. At first, the reconstruction of wave parameters from several random points in space has been tested, simulating the presence of various in situ measurements. Linear, spline and RBF interpolators have been compared and it has been shown that, when the number of measurements is enough, the linear interpolator results as the most accurate, while going towards higher levels of sparsity the RBF starts outperforming the others, especially in terms of robustness. Then measurements taken by satellites have been emulated as random lines passing over the area and recording the parameters only where they have passed. When having measurements disposed along random

lines instead of random points, the traditional interpolation algorithms fails to provide satisfactory results. Instead, a Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) algorithm is used since it performs significantly better than the traditional ones with this setup. GPRs have been shown able to reconstruct wind and wave parameters also with only 5 passing lines, giving an equivalent error of around 10% for the wave and 20% for the wind parameters.

LINKS/ADS: has evolved in the project along two distinct lines, sharing a common thread of harnessing the power of artificial intelligence. Significant resources have been directed towards applying AI techniques to analyse satellite navigation signals (task 4.3). In task 4.2, ADS, with the support of DIST, has pushed the boundaries, pioneering novel methodologies that exploit the combination of space data with 3D photogrammetric models, leveraging AI to extract urban features or land cover at multiple scales. This innovative approach allows for a comprehensive and detailed analysis of contemporary cities, enhancing overall urban efficiency. The deployment of these advanced competencies in environmental resources and urban planning has laid the foundation for a new era of cutting-edge space technologies, highlighting the critical significance of integrating artificial intelligence in the development and management of modern space systems. After conducting a thorough analysis of the potential applications of the surveyed 3D point clouds in a city area, our focus shifted towards exploring both nadiral and non-nadiral meshes. This strategic shift aimed to pursue an integrated approach of point cloud and high-resolutions images that promise to yield greater benefits. These refined techniques, along with their findings, are slated for publication. They will serve as the cornerstone of the support extended to the northwestern business ecosystem, facilitated through the NODES initiative.

Polito/DIST: In the pursuit of efficient urban mapping and monitoring, ongoing national project continues to explore innovative avenues, particularly in the realm of Digital Twins and Artificial Intelligence (AI) feature extraction. Our recent efforts have focused on the integration of cutting-edge technologies, specifically mobile mapping and aerial photogrammetry, into the high resolution 3D model derived in the first phase of the project, to enhance the accuracy and cost-effectiveness of model itself for various applications conveying to verticalizations devoted to Digital twin implementation. Our research has homed in on Castello del Valentino, a UNESCO heritage building in Torino, Italy, as our test area. Leveraging mobile camera-based Close-Range Photogrammetry (CRP), we captured a total of 79 images with the Google Pixel 6A camera and 82 images with the iPhone 13 camera, maintaining a constant distance of 5m from the building during data acquisition. These images were meticulously processed using the Camera Calibrator toolbox in MATLAB and Agisoft Metashape software, culminating in a georeferenced dense point cloud. A novel approach was devised, integrating DEMs from ground-based CRP and aerial photogrammetry. Utilizing the obtained Digital Terrain Model (DTM) from CRP and Digital Surface

Model (DSM) from aerial photogrammetry, we performed raster subtraction operations (DSM-DTM) to estimate building heights. This innovative fusion of data sources not only resulted in accurate height estimations but also showcased a cost-efficient alternative to LiDAR technology, particularly where moderate accuracy suffices. Our findings underscore the viability of mobile phone-based CRP coupled with aerial photogrammetry as a pragmatic alternative to LiDAR technology. This amalgamation not only ensures cost efficiency but also positions us on the forefront of digital twin implementation and AI-driven feature extraction, paving the way for scalable and accurate urban mapping solutions.

[Task 4.3 Navigation and Geo-Positioning services](#)

Polito/DET: During this period the activity addressed the study of new signals suitable to the use in modern GNSS system, focusing on LEO-PNT architecture and the use not only of the classical L-Band, but also S-Band and Ka/Ku bands allowing the use of wideband signals. A study to identify the best candidates have been performed taking into account different metric (Gabor Bandwidth, robustness to multipath and interference, complexity). Specific studies addressed the Multilevel Coded Spreading Symbols modulations.

Regarding the set-up of the lab facilities, a GNSS monitoring station has been purchased and installed in a shared lab in the facilities of LINKS. The system has been named N-SMART (Navigation Signals Monitoring, Analysis, and Recording Tool) and it is an open architecture for a reliable, high-fidelity recording of the GNSS signals based on Software-Defined Radio (SDR) Docker containers. At the center of its hardware architecture, Network Attached Storage (NAS) serves as the system's core, hosts the Docker containers of the required applications, and stores the collected data, making it the central repository for all recorded signals. The Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) front-end is used to perform the ADC conversion of the input signal. A Docker container has been created in its software architecture to host the GNU radio and UHD libraries, the scripts used for the grabbing routine, and the other container to host the multi-purpose web application. N-SMART can provide intermediate-frequency (IF) high-fidelity, In-phase/Quadrature (IQ) signal samples that can be used as input for further processing the quality of the GNSS measurements. A machine learning engine based on Convolutional Neural Networks has been implemented and hosted in a docker of the system in order to test detection and classification algorithms for GNSS interference.

LINKS/ADS: In close collaboration with Polito/DET we have embarked on the creation of a specialized laboratory dedicated to harnessing the power of artificial intelligence (AI) for GNSS signal analysis, with a primary focus on combatting jamming and spoofing vulnerabilities. Over the recent months, alongside our commitment to supporting the deployment of the monitoring station described earlier, we have gone a step further by establishing comprehensive laboratory

setups that enable a multifaceted approach to this critical issue. The first facet of this initiative involves pushing the boundaries of current GNSS signal analysis techniques by integrating AI technologies. By doing so, we seek to enhance the state-of-the-art methodologies for detecting, mitigating, and responding to potential GNSS signal disruptions, such as jamming and spoofing attacks or multipath issues. Our team is dedicated to developing cutting-edge AI models that can better recognize and address these challenges, ultimately improving the reliability and accuracy of GNSS products. In parallel, our second approach is oriented towards local businesses, aiming to educate and empower them to tackle these problems. This outreach entails providing training and workshops, imparting knowledge and skills to safeguard against GNSS vulnerabilities. Furthermore, according to the general objective of NODES, we are actively engaged in identifying practical, real-world scenarios where the application of AI-enhanced GNSS analysis can lead to tangible benefits, either by optimizing existing operational systems or by fostering the emergence of entirely new ventures in this evolving market sector. Our commitment to promoting innovation and strengthening the local technological ecosystem is grounded in the belief that these advances will bolster the resilience of critical infrastructure and nurture the growth of new business opportunities within this domain.

[Task 4.4. Space Exploration](#)

Polito/DET: Review of the latest updates of the LUNANET documentation of NASA and the latest advancements of the Moonlight initiative of the European Space Agency, defining the architectures foreseen for the Lunar communication and navigation systems, in order to prepare the simulation/emulation environment to be implemented in the Space4You lab.

UniTO/Dept. Physics: The tests on the set up of the X-ray Calibration Facility (XCF), hosted in the Physics Department (UniTO) for the characterization of innovative X-ray sensors, are continuing and have benefitted from the hiring of a new Technologist.

A first-generation Gas Pixel Detector (GPD) is currently under test in our facility; its performances are under study and will be compared with those of GPD on board of IXPE.

The track reconstruction algorithm adopted by the IXPE collaboration has been studied in detail, with the aim of investigating possible improvements for future X-ray polarimetry missions. A Machine Learning-based approach has been recently designed and has been tested on lab and flight data. In the next future it will be also applied to detectors tested in the XCF lab.

Output and results:

Research results

POLITO/DET: Implementation of the GNSS Monitoring station. Two Journal papers submitted on the topic

Polito/DET: Initial version of the event-driven simulator for the space communication links

UniTO/DipFisica: Set up of the X-ray Calibration Facility (XCF)

PoliTO/DIST: high resolution 3D model and Digital twin implementation.

PoliTO/DIST: high resolution 3D model Digital twin implementation.

Presentation at conferences

UniTO/DipFisica:

- 1 presentation at the international conference AstroInformatics (Napoli, 1-6 October 2023)
- 1 presentation at the "Riunione di avanzamento per i programmi ASI di astrofisica delle alte energie in fase operativa" (ASI Roma, 19-20 October 2023)

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations from initial planning

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

- Hardware for the implementation of the GNSS monitoring station (N-SMART)

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

PoliTO DET and **LINKS/ADS:** start of the test campaign using the implemented N-SMART station to test the algorithms for interference detection and classification of GNSS interference

UniTO/Physics Application of the designed algorithm to detectors tested in the XCF lab.

PoliTO/DET: setup of the simulation environment compliant to the LUNANET architecture

Key Indicators for Research activities and Flagship Projects in the period:

Outcome	Number of Pilot Line / Demonstrators / Prototypes	2
	Number of publications	2 journal publications 2 conferences
	Number of registered IPR (patents, utility models, trademarks, industrial designs)	1 Spinoff: MESPAC s.r.l. 1 patent application: 102023000019161
Output	Number of professor and researcher involved	46
	Personnel effort dedicated to Research and Innovation and Flagship Project	57,22

2. IMPACT

The outcomes expected from the development of the Space4You lab is of course the creation of a new asset in the ecosystem. The actions taken in the research module 0 will foster its sustainability beyond the duration of this specific project, making it a reference point for the research in the Space field. The pilot projects funded to the SMEs will provide proof-of-concepts, pre-developments, innovative technologies, that will represent the tangible results of the work that has been possible thanks to the support of Space4You in terms of knowledge and facilities, and such innovative solution that can then be further developed by each participant.

This meets the NODES's objective of fostering joint research and innovative activities by universities and companies as well as increasing the business potential in terms of creation and acceleration of high- tech start-ups, development of new/enhanced product/services and/or improved industrial process.

The applications of space technologies and data can generate impacts across multiple fields of interest for the ecosystems and the related spokes, including precision agriculture, environmental monitoring, new services for mobility, new services for heritage and cultural assets, thus enlarging the range of potential involved SMEs beyond the classical pool of aerospace companies.

Space4You will be also specifically promoted towards university spin-offs University spin-off to foster their consolidation in terms of knowledge and innovative solutions, jointly with the actions of the other boosters of the spoke that will address other aspects needed to bring them to maturity.

The creation of new innovative businesses in aerospace will be boosted by the European Space Agency Business Incubation Center Turin (ESABIC Turin www.esabic-turin.it), launched in 2021 and managed by I3P – the Business Incubator of Politecnico di Torino, in partnership with Politecnico di Torino and LINKS foundation. The ESABIC Turin supports new space-related ventures operating both in upstream and downstream space segments and has gathered a very large network of supporting corporates, research centers, financial operators and investment funds. ESABIC Turin will represent a local key asset for the translation of applied research outcomes into new high-growth businesses. and it will represent a natural further opportunity for the spin-offs that will benefit of the Space4You support.

3. INDUSTRY PARTICIPATION AND INNOVATIONS (prototypes, clinical trials, Testing activities etc)

Industry has been involved in the Space4You, both during the design phase of the flagship project and it is being involved during this first year set-up phase. Its core involvement is anyway foreseen in the next months as a “user” of the knowledge and facilities of the lab, also leveraging on the results of the cascaded call.

In particular, some large Enterprises have already endorsed the overall NODES project when it was submitted while the project partners are continuing to activate and involve more companies during the project activities. In the next months the organizational definition of the lab will be better defined thanks to the interaction and feedbacks of the Stakeholder Committee in order to match the industry needs. In particular, the stakeholder committee will collaborate with the Spoke on the development of the Flagship projects in order to strengthen collaboration among companies and universities in the implementation and development of projects expanding existing cooperation into strategic innovation partnerships.

In terms of involvement of the industrial network the NODES partners involved in Space4You have a network of large and small enterprises with whom they collaborate constantly, some of these being key players in the Space field. Furthermore, collaborations with different national and European networks (Italian Technology Clusters, European Clusters, Enterprise Europe Network, Horizon Europe European Partnerships, EDIHs, EITs, etc.) are/will be put in place to assure direct contact and contribution of major companies in the different activities.

4. FOLLOW-UP OF RECOMMENDATIONS AND COMMENTS FROM PREVIOUS REVIEW(S) (IF APPLICABLE)

N/A

5. OPEN SCIENCE PRACTISES AND UPDATE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (IF APPLICABLE)

Description of Open Science Practises adopted in the reporting period and Data Management Plan updates (if applicable). Table in annexes.

6. RESULTS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

Space4You aims at providing access to leading edge technologies and infrastructures, being a reference point for the company in the territory and beyond.

ANNEXES

A) LIST OF DELIVERABLES

Add actual delivery dates (or new due date for late deliverables, together with an explanation for the delay). In the Comments, please indicate if the deliverable was achieved as planned or not.

The labels used mean:

Public — fully open; Sensitive — limited; R – Restricted; C – Confidential; S – Secret.

D. No	Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Status	Comments
D1	Space4You Lab description	RM0	PoliTO	R	PU	M7	M9	M11 (04/08/2023)	Delivered	Description of the organisational setup of the lab
D2	Space4You Lab User Guide	RM0	PoliTO	R	SEN	M15	M18			Description of the lab facilities and expertise
D3	Space4You Executive Summary Report	RM0	PoliTO	R	PU	M15 (draft) M36 (final)	M18 (draft) M36 (final)			Description of the pilot projects completed within the activity of the lab
D4	Space4You website	RM0	PoliTo	O	PU	M7	M13			

Table 1: Deliverables

B) LIST OF MILESTONES

Milestone No	Milestone Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Date Achieved	Comments
MS0	Milestone 0	RM0	PolITO		31/12/2022		31/01/2023	YES	Preparation of activity
MS1	Milestone 1	RM0	PolITO	Issue of deliverable D1 Issue of draft version of deliverable D4	30/04/2023	30/11/2023		NO	Achievement of the milestone is delayed due to the delay in the delivery of D4
MS2	Milestone 2	RM0	PolITO	Issue of draft version of deliverable D2 Setup of 2 (TBC) pilot projects	31/12/2023	31/03/2024	-	-	Achievement of the milestone will be delayed due to the delay in the delivery of D2 and the setup of the pilot projects
MS3	Milestone 3	RM0	PolITO	Issue of final version of deliverables D2, D3 and D4	30/09/2025	-	-	-	No delay expected as of today

Table 2: Milestones

C) LIST OF CRITICAL RISKS

State of play: Give the state of play of the risks that were identified (and new risks that materialised during project implementation) and add new mitigation measures, if needed.

Risk No	Description of risk	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?	Did your risk materialize?	Comments
01	Non-fulfilment or poor engagement of partners on tasks <i>Likelihood: Low</i> <i>Severity: Low</i>	YES	NO	-
02	Partner withdrawal <i>Likelihood: Low</i> <i>Severity: Low</i>	YES	NO	
03	Potential impact of COVID-19 pandemic on project implementation. <i>Likelihood: Low</i> <i>Severity: Medium</i>	YES	NO	
04	Impact of the global economic crisis and ongoing shortage of electrical components and hardware needed for the setting of the lab facilities <i>Likelihood: High</i> <i>Severity: High</i>	YES	NO	

Table 3: Risks

D) PROJECT PATHWAY TO IMPACT: RESULTS

Name	Result type	TRLs	Steps undertaken towards exploitation (multiple choice)	Market maturity (state of the market targeted by this result)
Space4You lab	INFRA	TRL7	Prototyping in laboratory environment Pilot, demonstration or testing Intellectual property management Market Study Other	Emerging

Table 4:Results

E) PUBLICATIONS

Type of publication	Peer review	Type of PID (repository)	PID of deposited publication	Link to publication (if no PID of publication)	Title of the publication (for book chapters: title of chapter not of book)	PID of publisher record	ISSN/eISSN (if book insert ISBN)	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number	Publisher	Month/Year of publication	PID of book (if book chapter)	Book title (if book chapter)	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	License type (CC BY or equivalent) [CC BY NC or equivalent] [ND or equivalent] [Other licences]
Conference proceeding	YES	DOI		doi:10.36688/ewtec-2023-619	On spatial interpolation of ocean energy source variables: A comparative analysis			L. Gambarelli, E. Pasta, and G. Giorgi	Proceedings of the European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference	Vol. 15]	Energy and Climate Change Division at the University of Southampton	09/2023			NO	[
Article in journal	YES	DOI		Doi: 10.1007/s10961-023-10029-7	When computer science is not enough: universities knowledge specializations behind artificial intelligence startups in Italy			Colombelli, A., D'Amico, E. & Paolucci, E.	The Journal of Technology Transfer		Springer Nature	08/2023			YES	
Article in Journal	YES	DOI		https://doi.org/10.3389/fmats.2023.1242480	Vat-photopolymerization of ceramic materials: exploring current applications in advanced multidisciplinary fields			Elisa Fiume, Bartolomeo Coppola, Laura Montanaro, Paola Palmero	Frontiers in materials		Frontiers Media S.A.	10/2023			YES	Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY)
Article in Journal	YES	DOI		DOI:10.3934/mine.2023099	The mixed virtual element discretization for highly-anisotropic problems: the role of the boundary degrees of freedom			Stefano Berrone, Stefano Scialò and Gioana Teora	Mathematics in Engineering	5	AIMS press	10/2023				Creative Commons Attribution LicenseCC BY 4.0 DEED
Article in Journal	YES				3D printing to support experimental activities: lessons learned from rapid prototyping of an electromechanical actuator gearbox		ISSN 1590-8844	Berri, Pier Carlo, Dalla Vedova, Matteo D. L. Aimasso, Alessandro, Ferro, Carlo G., Maggiore,	International Journal of Mechanics and Control	24	Levrotto e Bella	2023				

								Paolo, Riva, Guido,									
Conference proceeding	YES				Experimental analysis of FBC sensors thermal calibration under different loading conditions		ISBN: 978-1-6654-5690-6	Aimasso, Alessandro; Gallone, Giacomo; Dalla Vedova, M. D. L.; Maggiore, Paolo	10th IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Aerospace, MetroAeroSpace 2023	IEEE	2023						
Conference proceeding	YES				Creation of a Support Software for the Development of a System for Sending and Visualizing FBC Sensor Data for Aerospace Application		ISBN: 978-1-6654-5690-6	Antonio Costantino Marceddu, Alessandro Aimasso, Antonio Scaldaferrì, Paolo Maggiore, Bartolomeo Montrucchio, Matteo D. L. Dalla Vedova	10th IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Aerospace, MetroAeroSpace 2023	IEEE	2023						

Table 5: Publications

F) DATASETS

Table 6: Data sets

Short Name:	SpaceStartups
Description of datasets:	Data regarding founding teams of 339 EU-based start-ups in the New Space sector. Data were collected from the Dealroom.com database for companies founded between 2013 and 2022, with at least €1 million in funding received. Data were collected from the Dealroom database. Firm-level data have been then integrated with

	individual data on the characteristics of the founders using information from LinkedIn. Each startup has been classified according to a large set of variables that include technological and industrial specialization, economic performance, fundraising capabilities, links with academic and industrial partners, geographical location, the educational and work background of the founders.
Data origin:	Dealroom.com and LinkedIn.com
Data type:	String; Integer; Boolean;Float
Data Formats:	.dta
Useful for whom:	The data were used by the DIGEP research group and were needed to validate the conclusions of a scientific publication
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	open access given data
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	SpaceStartups.dta
Accessibility:	Fully open à repository
Interoperability:	Standards for interoperability
Reusability:	Licensing and restrictions, repository for long term preservation
Open	YES

Short Name:	SpaceInvestors
Description of datasets:	Investor data from 339 EU-based start-ups in the new space sector. Data was collected and complemented on the basis of the 'SpaceStartup' database. The company-level data was then supplemented with individual investor data using LinkedIn information. Each investor was classified according to type, e.g. venture capital, angel investor, etc.
Data origin:	Dealroom.com and LinkedIn.com
Data type:	String; Integer; Boolean; Float
Data Formats:	.dta
Useful for whom:	The data were used by the DIGEP research group and were needed to validate the conclusions of a scientific publication
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	open access given data
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	SpaceInvestors.dta
Accessibility:	Fully open à repository
Interoperability:	Standards for interoperability
Reusability:	Licensing and restrictions, repository for long term preservation
Open	YES

G) INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPRs)

Type of IP Rights	Application Title	Application Reference	Application Date	IPR Owner	IPR Status Has protection been awarded?	IPR Award Reference ID
Patent	Sistema e metodo per la determinazione di dati meteorologici e/o ambientali di un sito di interesse	IT 102023000019161	18/09/2023	Mattiazzo Giuliana, Giorgi Giuseppe, Cervelli Giulia, Pasta Edoardo, Gulisano Andrea	NO	-

Table 7: IPRs

H) OTHER RESULTS

Type of result	Description	If the result is needed to validate the conclusions of a publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make your output available, either in digital or physical form?	TRLs	Type of PID (if available)	PID (if available)	URL to repository landing page for the result service/webpage hosting the result (if available)	What license is the result under
Software	DroneSim Simulator of a network of mobile nodes		TRL2			https://github.com/paolo-giaccone/DronetSim/	Open source: GNU General Public License v2.0
Software	Routines for numerical computations of stability indicators to facilitate the clustering of the orbits		TRL2			https://github.com/LimenResearch/norbit	Open source: GNU General Public License v2.0
Prototype	N-SMART: GNSS monitoring station		TRL 7				

Table 8: Other results

I) IMPACT in terms of TRLs, SDGs, KSOs

Technology readiness level of the project	
At project' start: TR2-TRL3 Current status: TRL 4	Expected by Project 'end: [TRL1- Basic principles observed] [TRL2- Technology concept validated] [TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept] [TRL4 - Technology validated in lab] [TRL5- Technology validated in relevant environment] [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment] [TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment] [TRL8- System complete and qualified] [TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment] [Not applicable]

Table 9: TRLs

Is your project likely to deliver results relevant for the following Sustainable Development Goals?	
Climate neutrality	[Not relevant]
Clean Water and Sanitation	[Not relevant]
Life Below Water	[Not relevant]
Life on Land	[Partially relevant]
No Poverty	[Not relevant]
Zero Hunger	[Not relevant]
Good Health and Well-being	[Partially relevant]
Gender Equality	[Not relevant]

Decent Work and Economic Growth	[Full relevant]
Affordable and Clean Energy	[Not relevant]
Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	[[Full relevant]
Reduced Inequality	[Not relevant]
Sustainable Cities and Communities	[Partially relevant]
Responsible Consumption and Production	[Not relevant]
Quality Education	[Full relevant]
Peace and Justice Strong Institutions	[Not relevant]
International cooperation	Full relevant]
Please explain your choice:	The Space4You lab aims at improving the technological capabilities of the industry creating a shared virtual and physical space where it can meet the applied research world. In this view it will contribute to the competitiveness of the companies involved fostering their economic growth. It is a space where improving education and training of students and young professionals. Space is by definition and “international environment” that requires international cooperation, especially in the research field. Last but not least all the downstream applications of space (communications, Navigation, Earth Observation) contribute to services that improve the quality of life and the development of sustainable services

Table 10: SDGs

Horizon Europe KEY STRATEGIC ORIENTATIONS (KSO)	Horizon Europe Impact Areas	Contribution to the KSO and the relevant expected impacts
KSO 1 Promoting an	A competitive and	

<p>open strategic autonomy by leading the development of key digital and enabling technologies, sectors and value chains to accelerate and steer the digital and green transitions through human-centred technologies and innovations</p>	secure data-economy	
	Industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people	
	Secure and cyber secure digital technology	
	High quality digital services for all	
<p>KSO 2 Restoring Europe's ecosystems and biodiversity, and managing sustainably natural resources to ensure food security and a clean and healthy environment</p>	Enhancing ecosystems and biodiversity on land and in waters	
	Clean and healthy air, water and soil	Earth observation applications have great impact in environmental monitoring
	Sustainable food systems and nutrition security	Satellite Navigation and Earth observation applications foster the development of sustainable services (e.g smart farming and agriculture)
<p>KSO 3 Making Europe the first digitally led circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy through the transformation of its mobility, energy, construction and production systems</p>	Climate change mitigation and adaptation	
	Affordable and clean energy	
	Smart and sustainable transport	Satellite Navigation and communications foster the development of sustainable services in transport market
	Circular and clean economy	
<p>KSO 4 Creating a more resilient, inclusive and democratic European society, prepared and</p>	A resilient EU prepared for emerging threats	

responsive to threats and disasters, addressing inequalities and providing high-quality health		
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Table 11: KSOs and Impact Areas - HE